

A Study of Complex Compounds of N-Benzene Sulphonyl Glycine with some Metal Ions. Part IV. Benzene Sulphonyl Glutamic Acid

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The compound N-benzene sulphonyl glutamic acid (RH_2) forms complex compounds with Cu, Ag, Zn, Cd and Hg. The blue copper complex is insoluble in water and has the composition $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})\text{OH}$. The colourless compounds of Zn (II), Cd (II) are soluble in water. The Hg-compound is insoluble and the Ag-compound sparingly soluble in water. They have the compositions $\text{Zn}(\text{RH})\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{CdRH}(\text{OH})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{Hg}_2\text{R}_4(\text{RH})_2$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{R}\cdot 2\text{AgRH}$. Compounds were soluble in alkali probably due to the formation of alkali metal salts of which only the Hg-compound, $\text{K}_2\text{HgR}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was isolated.

In continuation of our work with o-amino benzene sulphonyl glycine¹, benzene sulphonyl glutamic acid has been found to form complex compounds with Cu, Ag, Zn, Cd and Hg. Cu-compound was found to have the composition $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})\text{OH}$. Zn-compound had the formula $\text{ZnRH}(\text{OH})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Cd-compound conformed with the formula $\text{CdRH}(\text{OH})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Hg and Ag compounds were of more complex nature having the compositions $\text{Hg}_2\text{R}_4(\text{RH})_2$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{R}\cdot 2\text{AgRH}$ respectively ($\text{RH}_2 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\cdot\text{SO}_2\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CH}\cdot\text{COOH}$). All the

above compounds are soluble in alkali particularly in presence of excess reagent, apparently due to alkali metal salt formation. But alkali metal salts could not be isolated excepting the Hg (II) compound, $\text{K}_2\text{HgR}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-Benzene sulphonyl glutamic acid: The benzene sulphonyl chloride was allowed to react with glutamic acid in presence of alkali. The reaction product was norited, filtered, acidified and extracted with ether and the ether was evaporated. The solid was finally dried in vacuum desiccator². The compound was recrystallised by dissolving in ether and on slow evaporation, m.p. 139° (Found: Equivalent weight 145.4; N, 4.64. Calc: Eq. wt. 143.5; N, 4.88%). It is soluble in ether, ethanol, water etc.

N-Benzene sulphonyl glutamic acid monopotassium salt: The solid obtained after evaporating off the ether in the previous case was dissolved in ethanol and titrated with KOH in presence of phenolphthalein indicator till appearance of colour. To the clear solution acetic acid was added. A white crystalline precipitate separated, filtered, washed with absolute alcohol, and air dried, m.p. 248°d. (Found: Equivalent weight 323.4; N, 4.14. Calc: Eq. wt. 325; N, 4.31%).

1. N. N. Ghosh and M. Dasgupta, *This Journal*, 1966, **43**, 545.
2. S. G. Hedra, *Ber*, 1891, **23**, 3197.

COMPOUNDS WITH METAL IONS

A. *Copper* (II). Solution of the reagent in water was warmed on a steambath with freshly precipitated CuO in the ratio 1 : 1. A blue precipitate was formed. It was filtered, washed with hot water; air dried and analysed. (Found: Cu, 17.20; N, 3.89; Cu(RH)OH requires Cu, 17.35; N, 3.82%.) On heating the compound at 110° the loss in weight was found to be negligible. Aqueous suspension of the compound had a pH ~ 5. It gave CO₂ with NaHCO₃ and the compound at the same time went into solution, yielding a blue colour showing the presence of free carboxyl group in the compound. The blue solution was evaporated with a view to crystallising the Na-salt, but a glassy mass was formed. The same was the case with K-salt.

B. *Zinc* (II). Aqueous solution of the reagent was mixed in a stoppered conical flask with freshly prepared ZnO (1 : 1), the latter being in slight excess. The mixture was warmed till no more ZnO went into solution. Filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness in a vacuum desiccator. The solid was powdered and warmed with alcohol. Filtered and air dried. (Found: Zn, 14.50; N, 3.12. ZnRH(OH). H₂O. 3H₂O requires Zn, 14.85; N, 3.18%). On dehydration at 110° it lost in weight and the loss corresponded to three molecules of water (Loss found 12.13; Calc. for 3H₂O, 12.26%). The compound left after dehydration was analysed for Zn and N and the result conformed with the formula ZnRH(OH).H₂O. (Found: Zn, 16.44; N, 3.54. Calc: Zn, 16.91; N, 3.62%). The Zn compound was soluble in water.

C. *Cadmium* (II). Cadmium complex was prepared following exactly the same procedure as in the case of zinc (Found: Cd, 26.05; N, 3.43. Calc. for CdRH(OH).H₂O, Cd, 25.99; N, 3.23%). The Cd compound was soluble in water.

D. *Mercury* (II). Mercury complex was obtained following the same procedure as in the case of Zn and Cd complexes. The analysis conformed with the formula Hg₂R₂(RH)₂. (Found: Hg, 34.85; N, 3.09. Calc. for Hg₂R₂(RH)₂.Hg, 34.60; N, 3.21%). Hg complex was insoluble in water. Potassium salt of Hg compound was prepared and was found to be highly hygroscopic. Reagent was dissolved in water and titrated with KOH using phenolphthalein indicator to a pink colouration. The solution was then warmed with freshly precipitated HgO in a stoppered conical flask. Filtered and kept in desiccator. (Found: Hg, 22.50; N, 3.12. K₂HgR₂. 2H₂O requires Hg, 22.67; N, 3.10%).

E. *Silver* (I). Aqueous solution of the reagent was warmed with freshly prepared Ag₂O till the latter did not go into solution. Filtered and evaporated in vacuum desiccator. The white mass obtained was treated with alcohol to remove excess reagent, if any. Filtered, air dried and analysed. It conformed with the formula Ag₂R.2AgRH. (Found: Ag, 33.48; N, 3.20. Calc: Ag, 33.51; N, 3.26%). It was sparingly soluble in water, pH of the aqueous solution ~ 5. It gave no effervescence with NaHCO₃.

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